

The Developmental Characteristics Of The Life Perspective Among University Students According To The Theory Of Latent Traits

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 19,2020</p> <p>Accepted: September 28,2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Developmental Characteristics, Life Perspective, University Students, Latent Trait Theory.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4302243</p>	<p><i>Life Perspective is considered as one of the essential determinants of individual behavior, especially in the youth period, due to its relationship to determining the professional and social destiny and because it is the stage of joining the adult world. For this purpose of the current research, to know the developmental characteristics of the life Perspective, the researcher prepared a life Perspective scale based on the Barclova. The current research relied on verifying the psychometric properties of the research according to the one-dimensional hypothesis of the theory of latent traits, and used statistical analysis by means of sanctity SPSS, using the T-test for one sample, the one-sample analysis of variance and the factor analysis concept (2018). The current research relied on verifying the psychometric properties of the research according to the one-dimensional hypothesis of the theory of latent traits, and used statistical analysis by means of sanctity SPSS, using the T-test for one sample, the one-sample analysis of variance and the factor analysis. The research concluded that the scale used in the research has one-dimensional and global honesty, and that the Perspective of the world as a whole, as well as the Perspective of the individual for the future, is not statistically significant.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The problem of the current research can be summarized from an empirical point of view that the life Perspective has not been addressed by researchers in the field of educational psychology and growth, and because this is a whole problem of theory and other procedural, and because it is related to a problem of contempt and sphere produced by the overall image produced by the values of technology, globalization and the dominance of image as the component Askaski to do my knowledge and to devise a lot more than theoretical information, and because education is no longer the preserve of the family, school and local institutions, the approach of this variable is a treatment of a methodological problem that the Iraqi library needs. The problem of the current research is that it dealt with (the Perspective of life) as a variable that has a great impact on the behavior of the individual and the pattern of his relationships. International universities have taken care of him, especially the Russian and American ones, and the re-reading of its behavioral components after the events of world trade in 2001 in America. And it was related to dismantling the cognitive structures and beliefs of the terrorist personality just as it targeted the normal personality. In addition to not dealing with the current variable and as far as the researcher's aspiration, another whole problem arose, which was the reliance of most of the researches on the classic theory of psychometry so that it does not take into account the meaning of the person who imposes its characteristics. Measured wisdom. That is why the current research aimed to identify the characteristics of the developmental characteristics of the life Perspective among university students according to a scale prepared in accordance with the theory of latent features.

The Importance and Need for Research

The life Perspective is one of the modern topics in the field of experimental cognitive psychology, as it has been studied recently by many scholars such as Petkhoof, Leontiev and Naysker, considering the creation, creation and preservation of the overall image that arises as a result of social, religious and political factors that the individual has been thankful for since He grew up as his own and defines each individual's age and method of processing information in the stages of his life according to the individual's age group (Victrov, 2018: 14)Bond and Leon have taken it as the public image, which is formed from childhood and plays a big roundabout The period of doubt is a chapter, and it is established after the beginning of the adult phase, and it consists of social and religious values, political and economic conditions).

The adoption of the latent hypothesis theory (the Ara model), which provides the possibility to silence the dominant dimension by using the hypothesis of long-distance narration, which enables the Bakhkath to know which factors dominate the worlds Perspective of the kidda of the community through the use of factor analysis represents a procedural importance that adds to the ethnic library the possibility of adopting the scale It is used

in the current research to link it with other variables, as well as the characteristics of the developmental Perspective of life for university students according to the theory of latent features.

The university stage corresponds to the youth stage, which is characterized by psycho-social developmental characteristics, represented in the readiness and mental orientation to join the world of archeology as a religion, professional self-determination and personal and social self-determination. Kiddie Cup in the university campus stage (74: 7002, Симоненко С.М), which adds importance to the current research.

Research Objectives

The current research aims to uncover the developmental characteristics of the life Perspective among university students by using the theory of the features inherent in preparing the current research scale.

To achieve the research goal, the researcher set the following sub-goals?

1- Is there a one-dimensional feature of the measured feature (the Perspective of life) by adopting the statistical hypothesis (one-dimensional according to the ARA model)?

2- Measuring the life Perspective of university students

3- What are the age and developmental characteristics of the life Perspective of university students?

Research limits

The current research is determined by the students of Dhi-Qar University for the academic year 2017-2018 and for the morning school.

Terms Definitions

1. Life Perspective

According to Yarosh Kifis Kaki (2012), life outloj is defined as an individual's vision of his life and the ambition of his vision of his relationship with the surrounding reality (natural and social), his relationship with the world as a whole, his view of touch as your acceptance, his view of your reality, his health as a living and professional situation and his relationship to the events such as life and destiny. He lives like this, including his stories and experiences. Definition of Katerinko (2017) В. Ф. Петренко systems and viewpoints about the conscious world and the place of the person in it, on the attitude of the person to the reality around him and him, as well as the basic life situations of people, their beliefs, ideals, principles of awareness and activity, And the value trends caused by these damages The social group and the individual are, in fact, the subjects of a scientist interview. (167: 7102,,). Ф. Петренко (Barkalova's definition) 2018 (В. Баркалова the vital meaning and the value orientation that crystallizes as beliefs that orient individuals' behavior related to what is perceived in doubt and believes about) the same - self-awareness, others - awareness of social reality, unseen factors - religious awareness, future Perspective - awareness of the future The individual, awareness of the world - the world as a whole ((В. Баркалова, 2018: 188).

The researcher based his scale and the consequent disclosure of the age characteristics of the life Perspective among university students on the definition of Barkalova 2018

After referring to the land of definitions and determinations of the concept, and in favor of its literature, we find that it includes:

- A. The life Perspective is a vital dimension that defines and directs the behavior of the individual.
- B. It depends mainly on what the individual thinks and believes, on his perception and interpretation of his vision, the private Perspective.
- C. It is a wisdom that defines behavior consisting of components related to the self and others, social reality, metaphysical factors, future Perspective, awareness of the world as a whole and global event. From this Perspective, the researcher will determine the components of his current scale.
- D. Latent features :Definition of Allam (2005), modeling the relationship between the level of a specific health of an individual measured by a given scale and his response to one of the paragraphs of this scale. It assumes that the silence involved in the exponent as a response is a power of a certain Noah, so that there is a relationship between the different levels of individuals and the probabilities of their response to the different scale paragraphs with a correct answer (Allam, 2005: 53).

Definition of Rizopoulos (2008), a function of the relationship between the ability of the individual in his latent trait and the paragraph of the adopted scale and represents the data for each paragraph separately (Rizopoulos, 2008: Defined by Taqi (2009), as a mathematical association that links the probability of the individual's response Correct response to the scale paragraph and show the ability that a group of vertebrae measures through an upward cumulative coupling, as this curve provides the probability of the subject responding to the paragraph in a valid form by increasing the individual's ability to answer in different levels of ability (Taqi, 2009: 18).

Chapter Two

Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

This chapter includes two main parts, namely the theoretical framework and previous studies. The theoretical framework is divided into two axes. The first deals with the measured feature (the Perspective of life). The other matters deal with two hypotheses, a model according to the underlying features.

First: Life Perspective

The historical roots of the concept go back to the literature of Russian psychology, where it was linked in the beginning with myths, then philosophy and religion, and was dealt with by social structures before it was studied as a psychological concept and considered as a determinant of one's behavior. Subsequently, the Russian psychologist Ilkus Yi Lantiv put it at the end of the twentieth century (сыктывкарт.р) at the end of the twentieth century (64: 3102: сыктывкарт.р) as the individual's attitude towards life and the world, then he came back as an independent concept thanks to all the experimental principles that gave the concept independence in terms of the behavioral indicators that Represented an opportunity to be measurable) (691. Неонтьев, 1994).

Within the scope of recent studies, M. "KoltkoRiver" linked the concept of the life perspective with the individual's view of human nature and the underlying social system (NepomnyashchyA.V, 2016: 11)). (The person's skepticism) 78: 4102, индрев.ю.л. After that, thanks to all the concept's association with value orientations, the research went to the concept of establishing the concept of self-organization and self-domination, then linking the concept to the personality as it is represented in two types of subjective meanings that the individual as a whole represents about himself and the real world, (the deep and rooted pattern of meanings). In the consciousness of the individual, the valley he left, and through him the life events and what the individual is exposed to in terms of experiences and attitudes (and) the surface pattern represented by the visual images stored in the individual's memory and his fictional history that he gathered during the journey of life) (691 Леонтьев, 1994).

Barkalova 2018 (8102, Баркалова) introduced the perspective of life in terms of the vital meaning and the value orientation that crystallizes as beliefs that directs the behavior of individuals related to what the person sees and believes about (himself - self-awareness, others - awareness of social reality, unseen factors - religious awareness, perspective Touching as an acceptance - awareness of the same as the future of the individual, awareness of the world - the world as a whole ((881: 8102, В. Баркалова) Description of the components that Barkalova referred to: After reviewing the literature on the components of Barcalova's concept of the life perspective, each researcher recommends a set of qualities based on The viewpoint is the same as ke or from dealing with the concept of the life perspective from the point of view of a large soul, and the researcher has concluded the following:

1. Self-awareness is one of the dimensions of life's perspective and is the individual's ability to know his needs and motives, set his goals, define his strengths, put their paws and know the limits of relationships with others who have deep or superficial relationships with them.
2. 2 - Awareness of social reality, which represents the individual's place and believes about the natural or social reality, and a perspective of life that is here to respect him for others, their opinions, properties, beliefs and religions, and their right to choose the basis of the life club that they see and appreciate and respect their beliefs, interests and rituals, even if they are contrary to his beliefs.
3. The perspective of life is complete with belief in the unseen, and that the events of life are not closed up by the cause and the immediate effect, but there is a higher will and predestination outside the planning of mankind and his aspirations, just as life is based on material considerations that require the individual to have a spiritual philosophy and mystical experiences with which he balances between what is material and what is spiritual, in addition to his need to taste beauty and to have a renewed aesthetic sense.
4. The individual's perception of touch as an acceptance and is related to his ability to plan and relying on knowledge and science to determine harm as his acceptance in a sedentary society. He appreciates the value of that, and the individual in it feels the existence of ambiguity for his professional and social future and for his psychological existence and security, but if the opposite happens, the individual will resort to tricks, Scotch behavior, and confusion. A large coin eats a coin that is not a check, and that the law and its strongest position to protect you from the abuse of laughter is forgiven, and that social justice does not exist.
5. Awareness of the world through the individual's perception of human societies as human societies that exist as social axioms in all cultures whose individual lord is suspicious and determines the pattern of his approach to others as values of benevolence and the pursuit of cooperation and scholarly sympathy and respect for the exodus and not to compromise the beliefs of individuals or to silence them and to consider them. Every sanctuary heritage is the property of the human race, and the rejection of violence directed at ethnicities and minorities - 881: 8102, В. Баркалова) (191).

First. Patterns of Life Perspective

The perspective of life has patterns that can be summarized as follows:

1. The non-scientific pattern: It depends on the individual's experience that is derived from the shared daily life style, from popular wisdom, or through the events and events of his private life and his experiences and what happens to the surroundings.
2. Scientific style: hard work depends on scientific thinking that is based on hypothesis and verification, such as experimentation and scientific observations based on recording experiences and making use of them in subsequent situations.
3. The emotional perspective: depends on looking at life poetically and moody, either optimistic or pessimistic.
4. The religious pattern: You depend on the vision of life on a tiredness that does not depend on science and stresses every contact with the place and the belief that there are higher forces that interfere with the destiny of the individual and his destiny, and that these forces have a dominant role over people and their future. According to this pattern, thousands of individuals possess a special state of awareness related to providing answers about existence, the end of the world, good and evil, and the truth.

Second: the theory of the features inherent in measurement

The analogy is according to the theory of the underlying seizures, based on the estimation of thousands of respondents in the measured wisdom in a form that is separate from the influence of the research study, which distinguishes it from the traditional theory of Qikas. The answers to the paragraphs or the associated wisdom thereof, it is logical that a skeptic who has a high ability is more likely to call to the answer to the paragraph that has difficulty and vice versa (Jones1993: 38).

This theory developed after that to form a pioneer in measuring psychological strokes and plastic test on the level of the SQUA, as it does not assume that the variance of the measurement error is equal to all individuals after applying the scale, and that it is possible to provide an estimate of the standard error for each individual and for each catch there is nothing to do with holding power adjustments) Ismail, (1994: 126).

The theory was finalized with four basic assumptions.

1. One-dimensional (One-dimensionality), which means that there is only wisdom that works to clarify the differences between the performance of thousands of individuals on a certain scale, and that is why it is called one-dimensional (Weiss, 1995: 72).
2. One-dimensional means that all the paragraphs that make up the scale are homogeneous and have the same underlying tone, and the paragraphs must be related to each other as the scale of the scale (Topczewski, 2013: 18). Removing the effect of the approved form (Hatti, 1985: 156).
3. The local independence of the clause: When a one-dimensional hypothesis is fulfilled, the local independence of the vertebra is a matter that is investigated according to Lord (Lord, 1980; 1987:111).
4. The presence of a local correlation between the vertebrae may lead to an inaccurate assessment of the vertebrate teacher, the measurement statistics, and the size of the examined, as it may threaten the validity of the bank that approved a bank in the scale bank or the preparation of (Hambleton, 1991: 1).
5. The characteristic approach of the clause: This assumption is based on the idea that the steady increase in the number of people with the highest degrees of the clause increases the likelihood that thousands of individuals with higher degrees of silence perform this paragraph. This curve is quantified by the paragraph characteristic function and symbolized by (ICF).
6. The hypothesis of liberation from the speed of the answer: This hypothesis is based on the idea that the velocity factor does not play a spin in the answer to the scale paragraphs, meaning that the answer to the paragraph or the lack of response to it is not related to the time of the test or given sufficient time for a response, so the nature of the response to the paragraph is related With equal wisdom, not quickly answered by the respondent(Al-Mustajeeb, 2001).

Chapter Three

Research Procedures

This chapter includes all the research procedures and methodology used, the identification of the statistical community and the selection of a representative sample thereof, the tools used to collect data, the popularity of the methods of preparing the scale in the current research as well as the statistical methods.

Research Methodology

Because the nature of the research, its topic and its goal determines Noah, the size of the data and the nature of the approved curriculum (Abdulrahman Zankana, 2008, 15). The appropriate case is in the case of preparing the measures and the WS as using them to identify a specific specificity of a given entity in the event that the research does not aim to establish the impact and does not require the definition of WAS as the use of experimental and control groups (Al-Assaf, 2010: 297).

Research Population

The statistical community consists of the students of Dhi Qar University, the school of As-Sakahiya, where the number of them is calculated according to the statistics section and the information base at Dhi Qar University, 10644 male and female students, distributed by a percentage of 56% females, equivalent to (5846) of the total total, while the number of males is (4802) (By 44%).

Research Sample of the Study

For the purpose of implementing the current research, it is necessary to pour out a sample that is representative of the statistical community. The researcher has approved a total sample consisting of (600) male and female students and is divided according to the following Table (1) Samples approved in the current research.

Total	Percentage	Females	Percentage	Males	Statistical Sample Analysis
400	%56	224	% 44	176	
200	%56	112	%44	88	Application Sample

The Basic Sample Statistical Analysis

The determination of the sample size of the statistical analysis in general is done according to the precedents and the literature for my opinion, which is confirmed in your mind. It is preferable for no less than 400 individuals if we want to obtain accurate estimates of the parameters, such as checking one-dimensional calculation by using a global analysis to find the differences between the proportions of the explained variance between the factors in order to ensure that the Kaiser coefficient is from the statistical significance of any Kaiser laboratories (-KMOTest). So, the statistical analysis of statistical analysis was reported (400), Kalpka and Kalbaka, by 200 Talbaka from the College of Education for the humanities and the same from the College of Sciences (Coaley 2010: 57).

Application Sample

The researcher cannot enter all the elements of the statistical community as it is not possible for him to do so, so he intends to choose a suitable sample according to the criteria of the reflection of the literature to it, and because the researcher used the theory of silence, which depends on the characteristic curve of the vertebrae. It is determined according to the "Nanli criterion" (Ajzen, 1991: 188), which is defined for each paragraph 5 MS as two responses (Nannlly, 197: 262). The score of the scale in its final form reached 35 paragraphs, so 200 male and female students were selected according to the Nanli standard to represent the application sample. In the current research.

Research Method

The researcher prepared a tool to measure the life perspective of university students, through the theoretical framework that was presented in the chapter every second, where the researcher adopted the definition of Barkalova (2018 В. Аркалова), a Russian psychologist who belongs to the trend of human-kani activity, which is a trend that has emerged recently Z is within the scope of Russian psychology, and this trend emphasizes the lack of separation between consciousness and activity, meaning that what is formed from perception, awareness and perspective that determines the behavior of a thousand individuals is acquired through the individual's life journey and his representations of the world and life, which is what I called "experience By adopting the recommendations, qualities related to the same view of the five basic components (1- Self-awareness, 2- Awareness of the surrounding reality (material and skeptical), 3- Religious awareness 4- Awareness of touches like the receptivity of the individual, 5- Awareness of the world as a whole - 881 : 8102, В.Баркалова).

After reviewing the description of how the components of the researcher had 37 paragraphs (by 7 paragraphs for each component), then the researcher extracted the characteristics of the psychometric vertebrae through:

First: honesty

- 1- Apparent honesty where the scale was presented in its initial form consisting of 37 paragraphs on a group of experts (6) news in the field of measurement, evaluation and educational psychology - Appendix 1) Two paragraphs were omitted and the other paragraphs were compounded. The vertebrae, or reject as such, and thus have become the scale consisting of 35 paragraphs.
- 2- Global honesty
 - A. The researcher adopted verification of the hypothesis of the latent attribute's theory through a factor analysis to verify a one-dimensional hypothesis according to the following steps:

- B. Before everything, such as the verification of the convictions of the problem through the operative analysis, the researcher must check the test of the ability of the correlation matrix for the factor analysis and make sure of the suitability and adequacy of a different eye size. -Test (), for the adequacy of the analysis, it was (65.) and it is in a certain sense that Kaiser has a honesty for a cake that is in the bagelgka 400 students and honesty is very good, as it should be bigger.
- C. As for the second strand, which requires that the Partlett test sphericity of be statistically significant and its significance means that the correlations matrix to silence is the unit matrix (similar to the relationships established between the vertebrae) and that it has a minimum range of relationships, and Bartlett's test aims to test the matrix as it differs from the value of Z. The results of the case study are that the value of Cartelect reached 431.548, which is a neatly calculated function according to the P-value of 50. at the degree of freedom of 199, the table below shows that.

Table 2 Bartlett and CMO test to verify the suitability of data for factor analysis

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling Adequacy		.65
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	548.134
	df	199
	sig	0.000

- After verifying the ability of the correlation matrix for factor analysis, the researcher found the values of the latent roots and the interpreted variance ratio for each factor, and the Varimax Rotation was used for the factors whose latent root values were greater than 1 and the number of factors was five and deciphered what Its percentage is 56% of the variance, and Table (5) shows the values of the underlying roots, the ratio of the explanatory variance, and the cumulative variance poured for each factor.

Component explained variance ratio = Latent root / Number of latent roots x 100%

Table (3): Values of latent roots and the ratio of explained and cumulative variance for each factor

Variance Accumulative Scale Percentage	Explained Factor Percentage	Latent Root	Factor
39.452	39.452	16.155	1
46.870	14.294	3.150	2
51.043	7.587	2.001	3
53.190	6.123	1.240	4
56.601	6.091	1.027	5

It is noted from Table (3) that there are five factors whose latent root value has increased by (1), which explains the percentage of the suppression of 56,601% of the variance of degrees for the life perspective scale, and that the ratio of the interpreted variance of the first factor and the proportion of the interpreted variance of the second factor is higher than The value (2) that is required by (Reckase, 1979), as a minimum in order to realize a one-dimensional hypothesis (Reckase, 1979: 223). Both Hambleton 2004, Hambleton and Rickis indicate that one-dimensional is an indicator of global validity, meaning that all measurement parameters correspond to an internal measurement of the size of the survey (Hambleton, 2004: 698).

D- Another indication of the global validation and verification of the one-dimensional hypothesis is the one-dimensional hypothesis of gratitude for the significance of takku'a over the worker, where it is thankful for the concept of takkur, which is used in the global analysis to indicate the relationship of the variable with each of them (Abu Hatakab and others, 2008: 196). The scale has a width greater than (04.), which is the saturation level adopted in the current research. Table (4) illustrates that:

Saturation	Item								
.463	27	.578	4	.659	2	.698	10	.779	1

.469	3	.550	13	.650	6	.673	21	.773	7
.455	28	.531	16	.643	12	.691	8	.766	20
.453	5	.511	31	.613	33	.684	25	.740	34
.441	14	.517	15	.612	29	.680	11	.721	9
.421	19	.513	23	.601	30	.661	26	.709	32
.401	24	.510	18	.600	35	.663	17	.706	22

Table (4) shows that all the vertebrae of the scale are saturated on the dominant factor according to the theoretical structure of their distribution on the scale, and by pouring it ranged between (104.- 977.) and it is pouring high saturations thanking it into a pour that explains a good amount of the interpreted contrast and this Thank you for the ability of the scale to measure the toxicity of the study, which is an evidence of the global validity represented by imposing a one-dimensional mechanism according to the ARA model, one of the models of the traits theory inherent in psychological measurement. From the foregoing, the scale is distinguished by the global truthfulness as well as the apparent truthfulness through the news.

Second. Consistency

The Alpha Cronbach coefficient was extracted to arrive at the stability of the scale according to the internal consistency index, where the reliability coefficient (18.) was a good reliability coefficient. After summarizing the psychological characteristics of the scale used in the current research, they poured the scale ready to verify the developmental characteristics of the life perspective among university students.

Applying the scale to the research sample

Presenting the scale in its final form, where it consists of (35) paragraphs and three alternatives (applicable to me, applicable to me, not applicable to me), I gave you hard work (1, 2, 3) respectively, and the most important ground for the number of grades (35 - 35) 110), the research sample of 200 male and female students was presented, and the total grades were calculated, where the scores ranged between (40 - 94). To verify the objectives of the research, the researcher followed the following steps:

The first objective: - To verify one-dimensional of the life perspective scale

All the researcher recommended that the measure prepared enjoys the imposition of a one-dimensional kiqua through the ratio of the variance explained by the ratio of the variance explained by the first factor that blamed 39,452 to the second factor that blamed 14,294 and the proportion of the interpreted variance of the second and third factor of 14,294, which is higher than the value (2) that is required Reckase, 1979), as a minimum, in order to achieve the imposition of the monotonous cake (Reckase, 1979: 223). Thus, the Bakhkath achieved the first objective of measuring the age characteristics of the life perspective of university students according to the theory of latent fatigue, as a one-dimensional loan is the basic premise of this theory.

- The second goal: - Measuring the life perspective of university students: To achieve the goal, the researcher investigated

The following statistical hypotheses:

- 1- As the researcher used the T-test for one sample, One simple T. At a degree of freedom 199 and a sign of 50 was retracted, which means that there are statistically significant differences and the arithmetic mean of the sample.
- 2- The researcher used the T-test for one sample, one simple T test, and it now shows the arithmetic mean of the scores of "self-awareness" with a sign of 19 compared to the mean of the hypothesis of 14 palms. 0.05 and a degree of freedom 199.
- 3- The researcher used the T-test for one sample, One simple T test. It now shows the arithmetic mean of the scores of "awareness of social reality" Blum 17 compared to the average for the hypothesis of the real palm 14, and that the value of the T-value of the sense of heart was 1.99 compared to the tabular value of 1.96, when Significance retained 0.05 and degree of freedom 199.
- 4- The researcher used the T-test for one sample, the One simple T test. When holding, significance was 0.05 and degree of freedom at 199.
- 5- The researcher used the T-test for one sample, One simple T. The test now shows the mean median between the degrees of "the individual's perception of touch as an acceptance." 96,1, when a sign of 0.05 is held, and a degree of freedom is 199.
- 6- The researcher used the T-test for one sample, the one simple T test. 1, when a sign of 0.05 is caught and a degree of freedom is 199. Table 5 illustrates this:

Table (5): T-test for one sample

Property	Mean	Hypothetical Mean	T-Calculated Value	T-Tabulated Value	Significance Level	Significance
<i>Life Perspective</i>	82	0.05	1.96	3.71	70	Sig.
<i>Self-awareness</i>	19	.050	1.96	2.01	14	Sig.
<i>Awareness of social reality</i>	17	0.05	1.96	1.99	14	Sig.
<i>Belief in the unseen</i>	16	0.05	1.96	2.29	14	Sig.
<i>The individual's perspective on the future</i>	12	0.05	1.96	0.851	14	Not Sig.
<i>World Perspective</i>	11	0.05	1.96	0.31	14	Not Sig.

The third objective: - Determining the age characteristics of the life perspective of university students.

The researcher verified the statistical hypothesis (there are no differences due to the age stage of the research sample at the level of 50.) And by using the One-Way-Anova analysis of variance between ages (19,02,12,22), the results were as follows: -

Table 6 Analysis of monolithic variance

S.V	S.S	f d.	M.S	F
b	1244100	K=4-1=3	144700	8.64
W	1054110	N-K=63	16731.90	
T		K+N=66		

From the above table, it becomes clear that the calculated final value amounted to 8.64, which is greater than the tabular final value of 3.184, which means that there are significant differences between the four comprehensible degrees of age, and by going back to the averages of the calculus, it was found that the mean of the calculation is capric for the age group (19) It was (72), and the age group (20) was (81), while the age group (21) was (93), while the arithmetic mean was (79) for the age group (22).The means are as the statistical agents: - The formal research has approved the statistical process of SPSS.

Chapter Four: Discussion of the results

The first objective: All the researcher recommends that the measure prepared enjoys the imposition of a one-dimensional quantity through the ratio of the interpreted variance ratio of the first factor that blamed 39,452 to the second factor that affected 14,294 and the proportion of the interpreted variance of the second and third factor of 14,294, which is higher than the value (2). As a condition (Reckase, 1979), as a minimum in order to achieve a one-dimensional hypothesis (Reckase, 1979: 223). With this, the researcher achieved the first goal of measuring the characteristics of the age characteristics of the life perspective of university students according to the theory of latent characteristics, as it is a one-dimensional hypothesis. Basic of this theory.

The result can be returned by returning to the literature on psychometrics in order to according to the theory of latent characteristics until a one-dimensional model in which the response of thousands of respondents is not affected and does not depend on the individual's latent ability and the degree of difficulty of the paragraph to which the individual is silent (Scham, 130: 216) Moreover, the adopted theorizing represents the life perspective that consists of five sub-directions, all of which are theoretically consistent with measuring one feature (see theoretical framework). The second goal:

Measuring the life perspective of university students: To achieve the goal, the researcher verified the following statistical hypotheses:

Property	Mean	Hypothetical Mean	T-Calculated Value	T-Tabulated Value	Significance Level	Significance
<i>Life Perspective</i>	70	82	1.96	3.71	0.05	Sig.
<i>Self-awareness</i>	14	19	1.96	2.01	.050	Sig.
<i>Awareness of social reality</i>	14	17	1.96	1.99	0.05	Sig.
<i>Belief in the unseen</i>	14	16	1.96	2.29	0.05	Sig.
<i>The individual's perspective on the future</i>	14	12	1.96	0.851	0.05	Not Sig.
<i>World Perspective</i>	14	11	1.96	0.31	0.05	Not Sig.

It can be confirmed from the above table that the world's perspective as a whole, as well as the individual's perspective on the future, are statistically insignificant, meaning that the perception of touch as the future and the model that moves the individual forward and gives him a drive towards the appetite for life and confidence in the future as a future is almost non-existent due to the fact that the students' destiny is governed and dependent on the institution. Incorporate the government, the quota and destiny, and that they are unable to determine their professional destiny related to job opportunities or employment in the grasp, in addition to their lack of guarantees for the future, as the literature confirms in this regard that the lack of a stable future contributes to a large extent to the dispersion of identity and the weakness of belonging and social connection, and that This applies to the individual's perspective of the world as a whole.

It also appears that university students do not care about the world as a whole, as they are not concerned with events such as wars and famines and what individuals are subjected to in other countries or regions of the world, because they are concerned about their own concerns and the personal and social doubts, as well as their lack of interest in your case any rights of seclusion and the rights of freedoms The public, according to what the theorizing adopted in the current research suspects.

The results showed that self-awareness, social reality and belief in the unseen were indicative of the respondent of the sample, and the theorizing adopted in the current research is thankful that positive religious orientations enhance self-awareness and silence them in the individual's emotional and social participation with the material and human world around him, and their occult experiences in helping them Thousands of people want to balance what is material and what is spiritual, as the world is currently witnessing progress in technological means and tools and an increase in interest in ownership in exchange for the return of being and meaning and the return of spiritual and moral values, and the exaggeration of the exaggeration of the metaphysical interpretation of events and problems that the individual is exposed to may mean inability to match reality and deal with it according to the logic of realistic analysis It is a double-edged slide that may contribute to the individual's adaptation to the pressures and threats of life, but it does not mean that he possesses problem-solving skills and living skills in the world of competition and cognitive competition.

Third Objective

It is evident from the results of the research that the calculated final value amounted to 8.64, which is greater than the tabular final value of 3.184, which means that there are significant differences between the four degrees of the four-wheel calculus, and by going back to the averages of the calculus, it was found that the mean is the calculus for the age group (19) It was (72), and the age group (20) was (81). As for the age group (21), it was (93), while the mean was (79) for the age group (22). Except for the age group 21, which asserted more of a deeper interest than others in the perspectives (the perspective of things, social concern, and the metaphysical or religious perspective). This can also be attributed this to the fact that the life perspective of that group has reached stability after the experiences that it provides in the previous age stages, and you have decreased in the last group due to the pressures of defining the professional and social destiny, which is an age group that parallels the experience of the last American inhabitants in The university, and facing the students after their graduation or their feeling that they will face the world around them with the model of an unclear future and that they do not have a clear vision about the nature of life after graduation.

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